

Excerpts for Percussion from the Brazilian Orchestral Repertoire

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Abstract

This article analyzes percussion excerpts in the Brazilian orchestral repertoire, highlighting their technical, musical, and stylistic relevance. Works by Brazilian composers like César Guerra-Peixe and Claudio Santoro offer challenges comparable to international excerpts, incorporating regional rhythms, specific articulations, and virtuosic demands. Focusing on the xylophone, snare drum, cymbals, and tambourine, the study emphasizes the uniqueness of Brazilian writing and advocates for its systematic inclusion in orchestral training, promoting greater appreciation of Brazilian symphonic music globally.

Introduction

Brazilian orchestral repertoire, although rich, is little explored in the academic and pedagogical training of symphonic percussion, which still relies mainly on European and North American traditions. Brazilian production, however, offers works with refined writing, high technical demands, and strong cultural identity, ranging from 19th- and early 20th-century composers such as Carlos Gomes and Alberto Nepomuceno to the post-1922 Modern Art Week period. Still, the presence of this repertoire in concerts is limited, and its academic approach lacks systematic study (Gianesella 2012).

This article aims to situate Brazilian percussion writing within the orchestral context, showing how specific excerpts can serve as pedagogical tools for technical and stylistic training. We will focus on four excerpts frequently listed by Brazilian orchestras—xylophone, snare drum, cymbals, and tambourine—and suggest other national works that fulfill similar functions.

Xylophone

The xylophone, part of the keyboard percussion family alongside the marimba, vibraphone, and glockenspiel, is one of the most requested instruments in orchestral auditions due to its presence in numerous works and the possibility of performing fast, virtuosic passages. Each instrument in this family has distinct characteristics, such as vibration mode, key materials, use of resonators, types of mallets, and range (Moore 1970).

The technical demands of the xylophone include rapid diatonic and chromatic passages, divergent hand movements, rhythmic complexity, rolls, mallet doubling, and the use of more than two mallets (Alford 1983). Many excerpts combine several of these challenges.

A frequent example is the opening of George Gershwin's *Porgy and Bess* (1935) (Figure 1), included in Brazilian, North American, and European audition lists. This excerpt requires time control, precise mallet technique, evenness of notes, sound quality, and attention to modulations, being fast and virtuosic both as a solo and within the orchestra (Alford 1983). The combination of technique, rhythm, and syncopated accents explains its constant presence in auditions.

Considering these characteristics, it is possible to suggest Brazilian excerpts that present similar technical challenges.

Figure 1: Xylophone excerpt from the introduction of *Porgy and Bess*. Transcription by author.

César Guerra-Peixe—*A Retirada da Laguna* (1971-1972)

Composed between 1971 and 1972, *A Retirada da Laguna* is one of César Guerra-Peixe's most emblematic works, though it is rarely programmed by Brazilian orchestras. It gained visibility through the "Brasil em Concerto" project (Itamaraty/Naxos), notably with the first participation of the Goiás Philharmonic in 2016, including the work on their debut CD (*Brasil em Concerto* 2016). The second movement, "Alegria em Nioaque", contains challenging xylophone passages between measures 85 and 100, featuring fast runs and unison sections with the orchestra, similar to those in *Porgy and Bess*, making it suitable as an excerpt for percussion auditions.

Figure 2: Xylophone excerpt from “Alegria em Nioaque”, mm. 85–100. Transcription by author.

The excerpt from “Alegria em Nioaque” resembles *Porgy and Bess* in tempo (120–130 bpm), use of sixteenth notes, and phrase modulations. Another movement, “Regresso Pacífico” (measures 59–71), presents similar challenges, with demanding mallet technique and a tempo of 120 bpm, though with a slightly more restrained character (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Xylophone excerpt from “Regresso Pacífico”, mm. 59–71. Transcription by author.

Snare Drum

The snare drum, or military drum, is one of the oldest percussion instruments, historically associated with marching and infantry (Marcuse 1964). It can vary in size, body materials (wood or metal), and snare (gut, metal, etc.). It is usually the first instrument studied by percussionists, serving as a foundation for technique and rhythmic reading. Its practice involves traditional Swiss techniques, including single and double strokes, ornaments (flams), and rolls, frequently required in audition excerpts (Alford 1983).

Snare drum excerpt from *Peter and the Wolf*

Another frequently requested audition excerpt is from *Peter and the Wolf* by Sergei Prokofiev. The snare drum is valued for evaluating a percussionist’s virtuosity and control, often used in the first phase of auditions as a “confrontation piece” to screen candidates.

In this excerpt, sixteenth-note triplets in 4/4, alternating with eighth notes and rhythmic precision, stand out, requiring an interpretation with a military character, described as “vigorous and brave” (Goldenberg and Cirone 2002, p. 12).

board instruments—and require specific techniques. They are mandatory in auditions, with cymbals and tambourine among the most requested.

Due to the variety of these instruments, it is impossible to master them all completely. Thus, although works after the 20th century explore Latin percussion (bongos, congas) and Eastern percussion (temple blocks, gongs), auditions generally focus on standard instruments: cymbals, bass drum, tambourine, triangle, and sometimes castanets.

Tchaikovsky—*Romeo and Juliet* (Cymbals)

Like *Porgy and Bess*, the cymbal part in *Romeo and Juliet* is frequently requested in auditions. It requires precise technique, careful timing, and short, homogeneous strokes, achieved by damping the cymbals against the body to maintain rhythm (Alford 1983).

Figure 7: Cymbal excerpt from *Romeo and Juliet* (Overture-Fantasia), TH 42, by Pyotr Ilyich Tchaikovsky, rehearsal letter E. Public-domain score.

Claudio Santoro—Symphony No. 7 (Cymbals)

As in Tchaikovsky, the technique required to perform this passage is essentially the same. The eighth notes are also played short, using the same damping technique mentioned by Alford (1983). Similarly, the passage ends with long, open notes. We can infer that the same technique studied for *Romeo and Juliet* can be applied to this excerpt from Symphony No. 7.

Figure 8: Cymbal and bass drum excerpt from Symphony No. 7, movement II, “Brasilia”, mm. 62–67. Used with permission of the rights holder (Alessandro Santoro).

Georges Bizet—"Aragonaise" from *Carmen Suite No. 1* and Emmanuel Chabrier—*España* (tambourine)

The excerpts from *España* (Chabrier) and *Carmen Suite No. 1* (Bizet) are well-known both in auditions and in music history, highlighting the influence of Spanish sonorities, especially in France, with instruments such as castanets and tambourine. These passages require a good sense of style and agogic interpretation to convey the colors and character of Spanish music. Technically, they are challenging: in the "Aragonaise" from the *Carmen Suite No. 1*, the tambourine maintains a constant pulse, demanding precision to avoid destabilizing the orchestra.

Nº 1^a Aragonaise.
(Prelude to Act IV)

Allegro vivace. (♩ = 60.)

Tamburino.
Triangolo.
Gr. Cassa e Piatti.

Tamburino.
dim. molto - - - - - p

6

Figure 9: Tambourine excerpt from the beginning of second movement ("Aragonaise") from *Carmen Suite No. 1* by Georges Bizet, orchestrated by Ernest Guiraud. Public-domain score.

In *España* by Emmanuel Chabrier, particularly in the excerpt shown in Figure 10, the difficulty arises from the fast tempo, requiring the percussionist to employ technical alternatives, such as playing the passage on the knees. As in the "Aragonaise", the tempo must be very steady and secure, in addition to executing extremely clear articulation.

sf

Figure 10: Tambourine excerpt from *España* by Emmanuel Chabrier, mm. 61–77. Public-domain score.

César Guerra-Peixe—*Suíte Pernambucana*

The *Suíte Pernambucana* reflects influences from Northeastern Brazilian music, with writing close to the original sound of popular rhythms, as researched by Guerra-Peixe. In the “Frevo” movement, the tambourine maintains a fast rhythm, using techniques similar to those in *España* and “Aragonaise”, including playing on the knees and soft dynamics in the opening measures.

Figure 11: Beginning of the last movement (“Frevo”) of the *Suíte Pernambucana*.

In a single excerpt from a truly Brazilian piece, containing traditional and folkloric elements, the composer presents writing that challenges the percussionist, requiring technical solutions that not only ensure accurate and precise performance but also highlight the musical character of the “Frevo”.

Conclusion

Nowadays, more works by Brazilian composers are being revisited and recorded, increasing access to compositions that were previously forgotten or poorly documented, although the number is still insufficient compared to the country’s concert music output. Interest in joining orchestras has also grown, and today there are more professional, youth, social, and church ensembles. Despite this, the repertoire remains bound to tradition, repeating the same excerpts and leaving out contemporary works that require modern techniques. The musician’s specialization process, centred on auditions, ultimately limits the percussionist, a situation also observed in orchestras outside Brazil. This research does not propose replacing classical excerpts but rather including passages that enrich auditions, especially Brazilian works that have long been under-explored. The aim is to expand the audition repertoire, ensuring that percussionists are prepared to perform folkloric passages or tambourine parts in the daily orchestral context, avoiding incorrect interpretations.

References

- Alford, E. E. (1983). “Identification of Percussion Performance Techniques in the Standard Orchestral Percussion Repertoire”. PhD thesis. The University of Oklahoma.
- Brasil em Concerto* (2016). CD. Orquestra Filarmônica de Goiás; conducted by Neil Tomson.
- Gianesella, E. F. (2012). *Percussão Orquestral Brasileira: Problemas Editoriais e Interpretativos*. Editora Unesp.

Goldenberg, M. and A. J. Cirone (2002). *Modern School for Snare Drum: With a Guide Book for the Artist Percussionist—Covering All of the Instruments of the Percussion Family*. Alfred Music.

Marcuse, S. (1964). *Musical Instruments: A Comprehensive Dictionary*.

Moore, J. L. (1970). "Acoustics of Bar Percussion Instruments". PhD thesis. The Ohio State University.

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